

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Athletic participation, time management and academic performance of student athletes in San Isidro, Leyte

NORDITO S QUIMBO ^{1,2,*}

¹ SHS Teacher III, San Isidro National High School, San Isidro, Leyte, Philippines.

² Graduate Student, National Teachers College, Quiapo, Manila, Philippines.

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Abstract

Athletic participation has been in a tight spot when juxtaposed with academic performance for decades of debates and empirical studies. Athletic participation critics would claim that it is detrimental to the performance of the students inside the classroom or "outside the court." This would often be opposed by sports enthusiasts claiming that this type of engagement hones the students holistically. This paper attempted to confirm that the existence of the time management variable can help boost the positive relationship between athletic participation and academic performance among 96 student-athletes in San Isidro, Leyte. High positive correlations occurred between athletic participation and time management; time management and academic performance; and, athletic participation and academic performance. This study also confirmed what is considered important and urgent by this group in terms of student-athlete activities using the Eisenhower Matrix of the ABC Time Management Analysis. Finally, it can be deduced from the time allocation results that the more the student-athletes stick to a time allocation effective to them, the better the results are in all three aspects being studied.

Keywords: Athletic Participation; Athletes; Time Management; Academic Performance

1. Introduction

Curricular activities in Philippine schools before the school year 2022 have been divided into co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. Co-curricular activities were classified as those in which students can apply competencies learned in the classroom teaching-learning setting such as monthly culmination activities of the Nutrition month held in July, Science and Math Month in September, and open symposiums held by the school where resource speakers are invited. Extra-curricular activities are activities that do not necessarily call for prerequisite knowledge from formal in-classroom learning processes such as affiliations to school organizations. The most common organizations in Philippine public secondary schools are the Supreme Student Government, Theater Guild, Music Club, and Sports Club. The latter, being the subject of the current study usually sells well to students who have been through athletic training during their early years who do not want to cut the practice, or even those who have been motivated enough to land sports scholarships that would get them through collegiate education, others do sports for the sake of doing it.

In recent years, academic performance and sports affiliations of students have gained popularity over correlational studies. Notions like student-athletes earning "a sound mind and a sound body" through sports participation claimed by sports enthusiasts have been rivaled by some people believing that sports participation hindered student's ability to perform well in academics because of their training and practice commitments rather than studying by themselves (Montecalbo-Ignacio, Ignacio, & Buot, 2017).

* Corresponding author: NORDITO S QUIMBO

Several international and local researchers seem to have supported this and even further added that there is no way that student-athlete sports performance success and academic excellence could happen at the same time.

A study on sixty (60) students claimed that there are four areas that student-athletes must commit to and focus on daily: academics, sports, personal development, and career development (Billonid, et al., 2020) and further cited student-athlete classification as “non-traditional” due to their sports experience, obligations and roles on campus (Sedlacek & Adams-Gaston, 1992).

While academics tags the students’ primary focus in the school environment, co-curricular and /or extracurricular activities could not be denied their function in creating well-rounded individuals since “our learners need outlets through co-curricular or extra-curricular activities to ease their stress, tension, and anxieties brought by the health crisis. Co-curricular activities have been proven to bring positive impact on the health and well-being of our learners,” Director Leila Areola, the Philippine Bureau of Learning Delivery (BLD) explained (Department of Education Philippines, 2022).

While the study of Billonid et. al. (2020) particularly showed that the relationship between sports participation and academic achievement of the student-athletes was a positive correlation and consequently proved that sports participation developed and boosted their academic excellence, self-discipline, mental/cognitive development, and class participation, this study seeks to find the connection between athletic participation and academic performance via time management link to further reinforce sports involvement’s potency in enhancing memory, student’s concentration, learning efficiency and eventually, academic achievement on a specified parameter.

The importance of time management over and across fields of practice cannot be denied empirically and practically. Various models and theories designed by many researchers gained popularity in the recent past promising systematic and efficient management of time mainly for heightening productivity levels of the multi-engaged individuals of a fast-changing world.

The ABC Time Management Model has been common among the student-athletes in the research locale and the proponent of this study is also very familiar with being a table tennis coach for almost a decade now. The ABC Time Management Model has been integrated into the training where athletes have been informed and required of the three fundamental ideas: Awareness of the fact that every second and moment can become a great opportunity if one is aware of its significance using the quadrants of particulars (daily activities) as important or unimportant on the y axis and urgent and not urgent on the x-axis (example in Figure 1); Believe, as an operating word that moves an individual to think that once his or her awareness of time and its value are important in achieving goals in life, one is halfway down the road to success; and, Continuation, according to Chowdhury (2013), using some tools or techniques that are required to put A and B into real practice to bring success in personal and professional life (Jinalee & Singh, 2019).

Significantly, this method also dictated the use of categorization of large data into groups often marked A, B, and C, hence, the name. Activities are ranked then, by these general criteria (BK101, 2015): A-tasks that are perceived as being urgent and important; B- tasks that are important but not urgent; and, C- unimportant tasks (whether urgent or not). This construct is best understood using the Eisenhower box named after Dwight Eisenhower, the 34th US President, who once said “I have two kinds of problems, the urgent and the important. The urgent are not important, and the important are never urgent.”

	Urgent	Not urgent		Urgent	Not Urgent
Important	1 Do	2 Decide	Important	Crying baby Kitchen fire Some calls 1	2 Exercise Vocation Planning
Not important	3 Delegate	4 Delete		3 4	Not Important

Figure 1 (Left) Illustrated how the Eisenhower box works. Figure 2 (Right). A sample of the basic "Eisenhower box" that helps evaluate urgency and importance. Items may be placed at more precise points within each quadrant

ABC Analysis is frequently combined with other models of time management. The most common association is with the Eisenhower principle where tasks are also evaluated using the same criteria important/unimportant and urgent/not urgent where: (1) important/urgent quadrants are done immediately and personally; (2) important/not urgent quadrants get an end date and are done personally; (3) unimportant/urgent quadrants are delegated; and, (4) unimportant/not urgent quadrants are dropped.

San Isidro, Leyte, a rural town in the northern part of the island, has been honing students who regularly participate in the DepEd sporting meets and who regularly reap awards up to the Palarong Pambansa levels. Some athletes in the history of the school were neither good nor bad academically since they quite stayed on the average margin. However, there were and still are students who were succeeding in both their athletic participation and academic performance.

The global pandemic that affected school years 2020 to 2022 may have stroke the awards list of the schools but never the spirit of the San Isidro athletes who managed to train on their meeting their coaches virtually. Some athletes graduated from the school during those years and landed sports scholarships in college, some stayed in training while doing tertiary education and some are still in the school staying true to their commitment to balancing excellence in their sports affiliation and academic performance by having a time management system.

Hence, this study was specifically aimed at determining the correlation between athletic participation, time management, and academic performance of student-athletes in the locality.

2. Methods

This study involved a total of 96 out of 135 (71%) identified athletes from three groups: high school students who are actively participating in sports training from the school year 2020 Junior High School and Senior High School, college students who have graduated from the town's high schools and are continuing their athletic practice, and college students who landed in collegiate sports scholarships. College students need to have no gap years in their education. The study's respondents are delimited to those who are contented by their guardians to participate and those who are of legal age and have consented to participate via online data gathering. Data gathered are interpreted regardless of age, gender, socioeconomic status, and other demographic factors. The study follows a descriptive correlational design. To establish the correlation between the three variables: athletic participation (a student's affiliation to a sports training program by the school for competition if they are in high school or a student's continuation of practice while in college whether they are in a sports scholarship or not), time management (ABC Time Management Model), and academic performance (general average from the concurrent grading period), the study used Pearson's r from the frequency and percentage tables. The quantitative survey questionnaire used in data gathering was validated via pilot testing.

The instrument consisted of four parts: (1) the respondent's personal information which may, in one way or another, confound the results in the study and therefore, can be studied separately (name, age, address, gender, school, educational level, specialization (regular or special program) track and course (SHS and college), and type of sports; (2) the respondent's application of ABC Model in general terms; (3) the time allotment for daily activities of student-athletes and, (4) the respondent's general average for the concurrent rating period (expressed uniformly from 75-95 and above, where 75 is lowest and 95 as the highest).

3. Results and discussion

The data gathered from the survey questionnaires are presented in the following. While some may appear as extraneous variables, they are included in this section for future reference.

3.1. Personal Information

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
11-16 (JHS)	42	43.75
17-19 (SHS)	35	36.46
20 and above (College)	19	19.79

Junior High School subjects differ from Senior High School subjects in terms of competencies and therefore, in difficulty index as well. So, this might be a confounding factor in students' athletic participation.

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Address Expressed in Distance (km) from the School

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-3	34	35.42
4-6 km	29	30.21
7-9 km	21	21.88
10 km and above	12	12.50

As expressed in kilometers from the location of the school, student-athletes who participated in the study are mostly, at 35.42%, living within 1-3km proximity to their schools.

Table 3 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Gender Preference

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	41	42.71
Female	39	40.63
LGBTQIA+	16	16.67

Almost half of the total respondents are coming from the Male gender and the participation of the members of the LGBTQ+ community is significant at 16.67%.

Table 4 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to School

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Muertegui NHS	30	31.25
San Isidro NHS	47	48.96
LNU External Campus	12	12.50
University/State College Outside of Leyte	7	7.29

Most of the respondents are from San Isidro National High School 48.96%.

Table 5 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Educational Level

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
JHS	48	50.00
SHE	29	30.21
College	19	19.79

The least percentage of the respondents come from the college level.

Table 6 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Specialization (JHS), Track (SHS), and Course (College)

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
JHS Regular	17	17.71
JHS Special Program	31	32.29
SHS Academic	11	11.46
SHS TVL	18	18.75
College -Arts and Sciences	3	3.13
College- Management and Entrepreneurship	5	5.21
College-Education	9	9.38
College- Others	2	2.08

The Special Program for Sports in the Junior High School has taken the 32.29% of the total respondents compared to the regular JHS curricular program. Technical Vocational and Livelihood Track respondents tend to be more than the Academic Track respondents. There were also more respondents coming from Junior High School than from Senior High School.

Table 7 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Type of Sports

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Arnis	15	15.63
Basketball	15	15.63
Volleyball	15	15.63
Table Tennis	8	8.33
Taekwondo	10	10.42
Wushu	10	10.42
Track and Field	10	10.42
Badminton	5	5.21
Gymnastics	8	8.33

According to the availability of coaches and/or trainers in the locale, the common answers of the respondents are the ones listed which means that types of sports not mentioned are not engaged in by the respondents.

3.2. Application of ABC -Eisenhower Time Management Model

The study specifies the use of the simplest model of time management. Applying the examples in the quadrants of Figures 1 and 2, the summary of data is as follows.

Table 8 Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondent's Priorities According to the ABC-Eisenhower Principle

	Particulars	Important	Unimportant	Urgent	Not/Urgent
1.	Attending classes of basic core subjects like Math, English, Science, Filipino, Social Studies, and the like	93	3	91	5
2.	Attending practice/training every day during designated hours	90	6	87	9
3.	Doing daily assignments and submit them on or before the deadlines	83	13	44	52
4.	Exercising or working out every day for maintaining physical fitness	65	31	8	88
5.	Studying for quizzes and major examinations	87	9	77	19
6.	Attending duly scheduled sports team-building activities	79	17	49	47
7.	Getting 8-10 hours of sleep every day	86	10	19	77
8.	Attending lectures and discussions of strategy related to the chosen sport	46	50	21	75
9.	Participating in the subject-related co-curricular activities dictated by the subject teacher/s	39	57	50	46
10.	Attending to relevant activities on the field, floor, and the like that are dictated by the coach	89	7	80	16
11.	Participating in other extracurricular activities that help them earn points for the core subject areas	33	63	31	65
12.	Attending the school's strength and conditioning programs for student-athletes	89	7	89	7
13.	Attending remediation or enhancement programs in school to boost academic performance	74	22	59	37
14.	Attending required sports camps, clinics, or workshops	54	42	61	35
15.	Create projects as requirements of the core subjects and submits them on or before the deadlines	62	34	54	42
16.	Participating in legal sports competitions in and out of the institution	91	5	83	13
	MEAN SCORES	72.50	23.50	56.44	39.56
	Percentage by Mean Scores	75.52%	24.48%	58.79%	41.21%

Mean (Important and Urgent): 67.16 %; Mean (Unimportant and Non-Urgent) 32.84%

There are sixteen activities that student-athletes are required to do according to cross-referenced studies (Chuan et.al, 2012; Gaston-Gayles, 2004; Tower, 2008; Trudeau & Shephard, 2008). A careful mix of core-related subjects (predictors of academic performance) and athlete activities (predictors of athletic participation) should be performed by every student-athlete if holistic development is the goal. Table 8 summarized the data of the 96 respondents when asked to do the Eisenhower matrix. 75.52% of them consider the sixteen activities to important and 58.79% of them consider the activities urgent or 67.16% of the total number of respondents consider the sixteen activities to be both important and urgent hence, they believe that these should be done immediately, and personally. On the other hand, the other 32.84% of the total respondents consider these activities to be dropped or deleted. The table also suggests that more

student-athletes have been balancing their activities to maintain their academic performances and athletic participation than those who do not.

3.3. Allocation of Time Per Activity

In the daily 24 hours of the student-athletes life, the following summary of data shows the allocation of time the student-athletes have for the identified related activities.

Table 9 Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondent's Allocation of Time Per Activity in a 24hr Period

Activity	Allocation No. of Hours	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Core Subjects Formal Instruction in School	6-8 hours	56	58.33%
	8 hours	25	26.04%
	8-9 hours	15	15.63%
Sports Training, Physical Fitness, Sports Lecture, and Discussion	3 hours	75	78.13%
	2 hours	18	18.75%
	1 hour	3	3.13%
Core Subjects Assignment Compliance	3 hours or more	48	50.00%
	2 hours	9	9.38%
	1 hour	39	40.63%
Sleep and Others (family time, socialization, etc.)	More than 6 hours	29	30.21%
	5-6	54	56.25%
	Less than 5 hours	13	13.54%

The allocation of the respondent's time for the whole day is reflected in Table 9 where 58.33% go to school and follow the basic curriculum requirement of 6-8 hours of formal study of the core subjects per day; 78.13% spend 3 hours for sports training, physical fitness, and sports lecture and discussion; 50% give 3 hours or more in the compliance of assignments; and 56.25% of them do sleeping, family time, socialization and the like for 5-6 hours per day. These statistics could tell us that the majority of the student-athletes are still within the normal number of hours of sleep requirement although can be heavily jeopardized by the other descriptors in the criteria, formal education requirement, sports training requirement, and school work compliance requirement.

3.4. General Average of Student-Athletes

The student's general average in the concurrent grading period is the measure of academic performance. The following table summarizes the data.

Table 10 Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondent According to General Average for the Concurrent Grading Period

Grade	Frequency	Percentage (%)
95-99	0	0
90-94	12	12.50
85-89	27	28.13
80-84	38	39.58
75-79	19	19.79

Mean (General Average): 89.24

39.58% of the respondents, the highest frequency so far, fall between the general average rating interval with “proficient” interpretation while 12.5% belong to the “advanced” level based on the DepEd’s guidelines (DO No. 31, s 2012).

3.5. Correlating Athletic Participation, Time Management, and Academic Performance

Using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, the following variables are measured by their strength and direction.

3.5.1. Athletic Participation and Time Management

Table 11 The raw data guides for Athletic Participation and Time Management Correlation

Athletic Participation (Means per Quadrant/No. of Comparison (2)) X	Time Management (Estimated Means of the No. of Hours Per Allocation) Y
r=0.92	

This shows that there is a very high positive correlation between Athletic Participation and Time Management.

3.5.2. Athletic Participation and Academic Performance

Table 12 The raw data guides for Athletic Participation and Academic Performance Correlation

Athletic Participation (Means per Quadrant/No. of Comparison (2)) X	Academic Performance (Mean of Scores Per Interval) Y
r=0.98	

This shows that there is a very high positive correlation between Athletic Participation and Academic Performance.

3.5.3. Time Management and Academic Performance

Table 13 The raw data guides for Time Management and Academic Performance Correlation

Time Management (Estimated Means of the No. of Hours Per Allocation) X	Academic Performance (Mean of Scores Per Interval) Y
r=0.87	

This shows that there is a high positive correlation between Time Management and Academic Performance

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The present investigation showed that while several factors concerning the demographic profiles of the student-athletes may interplay in the relationships of athletic participation, time management, and academic performance, this study also confirmed that the time management method used by the student-athletes in the amount of time they allotted for themselves to do the identified basic student-athlete activities are significantly affecting their academic performance in a certain level.

Activities like attending classes of basic core subjects like Math, English, Science, Filipino, Social Studies and the like; attending practice/training every day during designated hours; doing daily assignments and submit them on or before the deadlines; exercising or working out every day for maintaining physical fitness, studying for quizzes and major examinations; attending duly scheduled sports team-building activities; getting 8-10 hours of sleep every day; attending in lectures and discussions of strategy related to the chosen sport; participating in the subject-related co-curricular activities dictated by the subject teacher/s; attending to relevant activities on the field, floor and the like that is dictated by the coach; participating in other extracurricular activities that help them earn points for the core subject areas; attending in the school’s strength and conditioning programs for student-athletes; attending to remediation or enhancement programs in school to boost academic performance; attending in required sports camps, clinics or

workshops; creating projects as requirements of the core subjects and submits them on or before the deadlines; and, participating in legal sports competitions in and out of the institution are activities that are both important and urgent to the majority of the student-athlete participants.

Furthermore, more than half of these participants spend 6-8 hours every day studying core subjects via formal education; 3 hours of sports training, physical fitness, sports lecture, and discussion activities; 3 hours or more complying with core subjects' assignments; and socialize and sleep for 5-6 hours such that the compliance of assignments may take up to 7 hours maximum per day.

The correlation between the three variables athletic participation, time management, and academic performance are of high positive correlation which means that when these student-athletes manage their time wisely, they can have higher academic success. It can also be gleaned that while one of these increases, the rest also increase, e.g. when athletic participation intensifies, the more they should manage their time wisely to balance academic and extra-curricular success rates.

Therefore, the results of the study will guide the school administration, staff, and teachers to give utmost importance to promoting time on task not only for student-athletes but for the whole student population.

The parents or guardians including the community can also be part of maximizing the potential of these young spirits by encouraging them to not only focus on what they can do to make themselves better.

Further related studies may also be conducted using demographics as factors that could provide significant differences in the academic performance of student-athletes.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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